

HUMAN RIGHTS AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL LAW

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Annotation: the article will talk about human rights, its problems. It also reflected the concept of international law and the protection of human rights in international law.

Keywords: Human Rights, Human Rights International Protection, International Law, Conference.

International protection of human rights is the sum of legal norms that determine and strengthen human rights and freedoms, the obligations of states on the practical implementation of these rights and freedoms by states, as well as the mechanism of international control over the fulfillment of obligations by states in this area of law and the direct protection of violated rights of an individual.

The problem of human rights is one of the most pressing problems of the present time. Human rights are the highest value, the anthem of society. Human rights is a comprehensive concept in which the aspirations, aspirations of all mankind are concentrated. Human rights are the basis of current development and the requirement of the era.

Human rights are the most important sign of a democratic legal state. Human rights are an important criterion indicating the level of democratic development of each state. That is why human rights occupy an important place in international law and in the national legal system.

In the process of human historical development, human rights legislation is a set of laws on human and civil rights and freedoms. These laws include international human rights documents and national laws. Human rights legislation has gone through three major stages in its development. The first phase, beginning with the French Declaration of human and civil rights of 1789, lasted until the first World War. At this stage, legislation on the personal and political rights of a person has developed in priority.

Special attention in the laws passed during this period is paid to the legal regulation of the following problems:

- freedom of the individual and equality of citizens;
- personality immunity;
- private property law;
- although suffrage is limited to various sezns.

The second stage includes the first half of the 20th century. At this stage, social orientation influenced by democracy, legislation on the socio-economic rights of people has developed rapidly.

Of particular importance were the laws on the right to work, the right to rest, the right to social assistance. Social legislation in France and Sweden, the Weimar Constitution of 1920, and the Constitutions of France and Italy in 1946 are prominent examples.

The third stage – dating back to the second half of the 20th century, at this stage the legislation on the “new generation” of human rights developed.

These rights include:

- peaceful residence permit;
- right to a pure and clean environment;
- includes the right to information vs.

At this stage, an international system of human rights legislation was formed.

Every state in the world has also formed a certain legislative system regarding human rights. The basis of this legislator is, first of all, the constitutions. Human and civil rights and freedoms are reflected in the current laws in the Constitutions of all states.

Currently, states have strengthened the following important provisions regarding human rights in their constitutions:

- recognition and protection of human rights and freedoms are public obligations;
- compliance of the catalog of human rights and freedoms with international legal templates and the priority of international law in this area;
- human rights and freedoms apply to him from birth, recognition of the idea, theory of a new natural law;
- equal and equal concern of human rights and freedoms to everyone and to everyone;
- provision of citizens with guaranteed judicial protection;
- the need for the implementation of human rights and freedoms not to violate the rights of other persons.

The legislative system of human rights in the countries of the world is divided into the following groups.

1. Laws regarding the personal rights of citizens.
2. Laws concerning the political rights of citizens.
3. Laws regarding the economic rights of citizens.
4. Laws concerning cultural rights.
5. International legal documents on human rights.¹

International law is a system of legal norms that regulate the relationship between states, national-liberation movements, international organizations, stateless structures and, in some cases, between individuals. International human rights law is the same branch of international law in which, in addition to states, a certain group of individuals and persons is also considered as a subject of international law. International human rights law differs in the same aspect from most other branches of international law. It is not for nothing that there has been a debate so far about the role of international human rights law in the international law system, as well as its relationship with other areas of international law, of course.²

International organizations are one of the subjects of international law. Today, there is no sphere of international life in which there is no participation of international organizations. Professor A.X.Saidov writes that in international relations, international organizations play an important role as one of the rational forms of cooperation of states. Therefore, it is impossible to imagine today's interstate relations without international organizations. At the same time,

¹ Tadjibayeva O.A. Ramazonova N.K., Inson huquqlari: o'quv qo'llanma.-Toshkent.: “O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati” nashriyoti, 2010. - B.7-8.

² Saidov.A.X. Inson huquqlari bo'yicha xalqaro huquq. Darslik. -T. : Konsauditinform-Nashr, 2006. -B.76.

it should be noted that today it is impossible to find a single state that does not cooperate with any international organization. Currently, there are more than 300 different international governmental organizations in the world. And the exact number of international non-governmental organizations is very difficult to determine, they are more than twenty thousand.

International organizations themselves are divided into international intergovernmental and international non-governmental organizations. It is generally accepted to divide international intergovernmental organizations into universal, regional, interregional international organizations, both in terms of their point of membership.

International protection of human rights:

- universal as an International Organization, universal within the framework of the UN and some of its specialized organizations, such as UNESCO, the International Labor Organization;
- interregional as an interregional organization within the organization for security and co-operation in Europe;
- as a regional organization, regional mechanisms within international intergovernmental organizations such as the Council of Europe, the European Union, the organization of American States, the organization of African Unity have been formed.³

The importance of international human rights conferences in the mutual development of human rights and international law is very important. Because such conferences, attended by state and public figures, scientists and specialists from all countries of the world, are often held on various topics. The range and number of participants in international conferences can vary depending on the topics that are raised in it.

Among such conferences, world conferences on human rights are important. At these conferences, the most pressing problems of human rights are put into discussion.

When it comes to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it.⁴

The 20th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of human rights was celebrated in 1968, when it was declared the International Year of human rights. The main event of that year was the International Conference on human rights, held in Tehran, Iran from April 22 to May 13. It was the first World Conference of governments devoted solely to a single topic. The call, adopted at the end of this conference, recognized civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights as interrelated and indivisible rights.

Another of the most important major events regarding the issues of comprehensive protection of human rights is the 2000 UN Millennium Summit. The Millennium Summit gathered leaders from 189 states to draw attention to global threats that could not be the most delayed. The leaders of the state gathered at the summit committed themselves to make this universe even better for the whole of insomnia. There has been a unique opportunity to unite efforts to combat poverty in states, improve the use of basic types of services, reduce the spread of diseases and protect the environment. The Millennium Declaration adopted at the

³ Mo'minov A.R., Tillabayev M.A., -T.: Adolat, 2013. 101-b.

⁴ Talantbek Madumarov, & Gulomjonov Odiljon Raximjon Ogli (2023). FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM). Educational sacrifices, 02-05 (1), 194-197.

summit set the global agenda of the 21st century and put forward eight specific goal-oriented tasks popular as Millennium Development Goals (MTMS).⁵

Monitoring of the Millennium Development Goals of the United Nations is carried out at the global level and at the national level. On the work done in this direction at the world level, the UN secretary general reports annually to the General Assembly. At the national level, reports on the implementation of Millennium Goals are published.

⁵ Mingyillik taraqqiyoti maqsadlari – amalda. //Demokratlashtirish va inson huquqlari. Ilmiy-ma'rifiy jurnal. 3-son, 2010,-B.2.

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